

GENUS OXYTROPIS DC. OF ALTAI MOUNTAIN COUNTRY

EVGENY ANTONYUK, ALEXEY VAGANOV

evgenijantonyuk@gmail.com

Altai State University

Dataset on GBIF

Access to the dataset

Description

The dataset contains an up-to-date list of representatives of the genus *Oxytropis* DC. of Altai Mountain Country (<http://altaiflora.asu.ru>). The dataset is intended to provide all interested users of GBIF with information on the distribution of the genus within the AMC, identifying the locations of storage of material in world collections and other types of analyzes (taxonomic, phenological, etc.) using the available datasets in GBIF.

Geographic scope

The database contains information on the distribution of the genus *Oxytropis* DC. of the Altai Mountain Country (AMC) within the territories of Russia, Mongolia, China and Kazakhstan.

Bibliography

1. Антонюк Е. В. Род *Oxytropis* // Определитель растений Алтайского края / [И.М. Красноборов и др.]; отв. ред. И. М. Красноборов; Рос. акад. наук, Сиб. отд-ние, Центр. сиб. ботан. сад [и др.]. - Новосибирск : Изд-во СО РАН : Гео, 2003. – С. 266-268.
2. Антонюк Е. В. Род *Oxytropis* DC. во флоре Алтайского края // Флора и растительность Алтая: Труды Южно-Сибирского ботанического сада. – Барнаул: Изд-во Алт. гос. ун-та, 1999. – С. 67–71.

GBIF registration

Registration date August 18, 2023
Metadata last modified August 18, 2023
Publication date August 18, 2023

Hosted by Altai State University
Installation altb.asu.ru/ipt
Installation contacts Alexey Vaganov

Licence CC BY-NC 4.0

Endpoints <http://altb.asu.ru/ipt/archive.do?r=oxytropis> (Darwin Core Archive) <http://altb.asu.ru/ipt/eml.do?r=oxytropis> (EML)
Preferred identifier DOI10.15468/udn74y
Alternative identifiers <http://altb.asu.ru/ipt/resource?r=oxytropis>

Citation

Antonyuk E, Vaganov A (2023). Genus *Oxytropis* DC. of Altai Mountain Country. Version 1.3. Altai State University. Checklist dataset
<https://doi.org/10.15468/udn74y> accessed via GBIF.org on 2023-10-05.

The research was carried out within the state assignment of Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation (theme No. FZMW-2023-0008).